

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

NEXTGEN
PROTEINS

Bioconversion of Underutilized Resources
into Next Generation Proteins for Food and Feed

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This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement no. 862704.

Effects of the partial replacement of dietary soybean with insect meal on growth performance, meat quality and ceca metabolome and microbiota composition in female turkeys

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Introduction

- Growth of world population is increasing protein demand (feed or food)
- **Soybean**: most important protein source in commercial poultry feeding
- Some aspects of soybean cultivation, transportation and processing are concerning from a sustainability standpoint (...at least from an EU perspective)

Interest in identifying **alternative protein sources** that might replace soybean in poultry diets while maintaining animal performance and health

Introduction

Insects: a sustainable source of feed proteins for poultry

- ✓ Capacity of converting “organic food waste” into high-value protein products
- ✓ Excellent nutritional profile
- ✓ Low environmental impact

Relatively scarce knowledge concerning the use of insect meal as protein source in turkey feeding

Aim

To evaluate the effects of the partial replacement of soybean meal with black soldier fly meal (BSF; *Hermetia illucens*) on:

- Productive performance
 - Breast meat quality
- Ceca metabolome and microbiota

in female turkeys

Materials and Methods

Experimental design

- Both groups constituted by 9 replicate pens of 84 turkeys each
- All diets were formulated to meet current nutritional recommendations (6-phase feeding program; 0-22, 23-50, 51-64; 65-78, 79-93; 94-105 d)
- Distributed in pelleted form and for *ad-libitum* consumption

Materials and Methods

Chemical composition of BSF meal

Composition (<i>as is</i>)	%
Dry matter	97.0
Crude protein	58.5
Ash	10.0
Total fat	6.00
Chitin	5.54
Calcium	1.90
Phosphorous	0.96
AME _n (kcal/kg)	2,626

AA profile (% of CP)	Reference [#]	
	BSF	SBM
Lysine	6.13	6.05
Methionine	1.81	1.33
Cysteine	0.90	1.43
Tryptophan	1.50	1.34
Threonine	4.37	3.86
Arginine	5.41	7.30
Isoleucine	4.82	4.56
Leucine	7.46	7.60
Valine	6.70	4.74
Histidine	3.43	2.59
Serine	4.53	4.99
Glycine	5.76	4.22
Proline	6.05	5.04
Alanine	7.53	4.31
Phenylalanine	4.51	5.10
Glutamic acid	13.14	11.4
Aspartic acid	9.95	17.9

Fatty acids

■ Saturated FA ■ Monounsaturated FA ■ Polyunsaturated FA

Materials and Methods

Ingredients and chemical composition of experimental diets

All diets were iso-energetic and with a similar amino acid profile (optimized on a digestible basis)

	Grower III (65 – 78 d)		Grower IV (79 – 93 d)		Finisher (94 – 105 d)	
<i>Ingredients (%)</i>	CON	INS	CON	INS	CON	INS
Corn	32.0	31.5	35.7	35.1	34.7	34.0
Wheat	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	27.5	27.5
Soybean meal	28.5	24.7	21.4	17.7	14.6	11.0
Soybean	6.00	6.00	10.0	10.0	16.0	16.0
BSF meal	0.00	5.00	0.00	5.00	0.00	5.00
Animal fats	4.48	4.12	4.50	4.16	4.20	3.90
Others	4.02	3.68	3.40	3.04	3.00	2.60
Composition						
DM, %	88.3	88.1	88.1	88.2	88.1	88.0
CP, %	21.6	21.8	18.9	19.5	17.9	18.8
Total Fats, %	6.75	6.68	8.04	7.73	9.56	9.32
Calcium (%)	0.77	0.77	0.67	0.67	0.60	0.61
Phosphorous (%)	0.49	0.51	0.42	0.44	0.36	0.38
AME (kcal/kg)	3,100	3,100	3,200	3,200	3,275	3,275
Av. Lys (%)	1.20	1.20	1.08	1.08	1.00	1.00
Av. Met + Cys (%)	0.84	0.84	0.78	0.78	0.75	0.75
Av. Arg (%)	1.27	1.27	1.14	1.14	1.07	1.07
Av. Thr (%)	0.78	0.78	0.70	0.70	0.65	0.65

Materials and Methods

Productive performance

- Body weight (BW), daily weight gain (DWG), daily feed intake (DFI), feed conversion ratio (FCR) on a pen basis
- For each feeding phase ad overall trial period (0-105 d)
- Mortality: daily

Meat quality

- 12 breasts/group collected al slaughtering
- Main meat technological properties (pH, color profile, water holding capacity and shear-force)

Ceca microbiota and metabolome

- Ceca content obtained from 15 birds/group at slaughtering
- 16S Amplicon Sequencing for microbiota
- ¹H-Nuclear Magnetic Resonance for metabolomics profile

Results

Growth performance (0-105 d)

	CON	INS	SEM	P-value
Body weight (g/bird)	10,057	10,173	103.9	0.04
Daily weight gain (g/bird/d)*	95.2	96.2	0.83	0.03
Daily feed intake (g/bird/d)*	203.9	204.7	1.93	n.s.
Feed intake (kg/bird)*	21.40	21.52	0.23	n.s.
Feed conversion ratio*	2.141	2.127	0.01	0.03
Mortality (%)	0.00	0.79	0.06	n.s.

* Corrected for mortality;

CON = soybean-based diet; INS = 5% insect meal from 65 d to slaughter (105 d);

n.s. = not statistically significant

Results

Breast meat quality

	CON	INS	SEM	P-value
Ultimate pH (pHu)	5.66	5.66	0.01	n.s.
Lightness - L*	50.57	49.59	0.27	n.s.
Redness - a*	3.89	3.88	0.15	ns
Yellowness - b*	2.83	1.95	0.22	<0.05
Drip loss (%)	0.89	0.85	0.02	n.s.
Cooking loss (%)	17.87	18.96	0.34	n.s.
Shear force (kg)	2.36	2.28	0.08	n.s.

CON = soybean-based diet; INS = 5% insect meal from 65 d to slaughter (105 d);
n.s. = not statistically significant

Results

Cecal metabolome (105 d)

71
metabolites
identified in
the ceca

CON = soybean-based diet;
INS = 5% insect meal from 65
d to slaughter (105 d).
* : P<0.05

Results

Cecal microbiota composition (105 d)

Relative abundance (%) at phylum level

α -diversity: n.s.
 β -diversity: n.s.

CON = soybean-based diet;
INS = 5% insect meal from 65 d to slaughter (105 d);
n.s. = not statistically significant

Results

Cecal microbiota composition (105 d)

Relative abundance (%) at genus level

α-diversity: n.s.
β-diversity: n.s.

Results

Cost *per kg* of live weight

Conclusions

- The partial replacement of soybean meal with **5% BSF meal** from 65 d onwards **improved the productive performance of female turkeys**
- **No adverse effect** of the dietary treatment was observed **on breast meat quality**
- **Ceca metabolomics profile showed slight but still interesting variations** in response to the dietary administration of 5% BSF meal (e.g. tendency for a greater production of butyrate), whereas **microbiota composition was rather similar between groups**
- Although further studies on this topic are needed, these results highlight that **BSF meal can be considered as a valid alternative to soybean meal in turkey diets although current market price still represents an issue**

Acknowledgements

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The logo for Amadori features the word "Amadori" in a bold, green, sans-serif font with a red dot over the "i".

Thanks for your attention!

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